

PAIRWORK IS A SUCCESSFUL TEACHING STRATEGY IN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Annotation. It is noteworthy to note that students get a lot of knowledge when they work in groups since they have more opportunities to connect. The best technique to gauge students' learning progress is through pair work. The teacher can accomplish this without the kids being aware that they are being watched and tested. Working in pairs increases the learners' linguistic productivity since it deepens and fosters a meaningful connection between them. The teacher cannot listen to all couples at once in the interim, but that does not mean that nothing can be done about it.

Keywords: pair work, classification, advantages, teaching strategy, pair work activities, task-based learning.

Introduction. Pair work is a method of class management, and the teacher's job in the classroom is to act as a facilitator. It is one of the strategies utilized in group instruction. According to Richards and Schmidt, pair work is a type of learning activity where students collaborate in groups of two. Pair work is described as bringing students in small groups of two or three to complete an activity together in the Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching. Numerous theories and methods of teaching languages stress the value of pairwork as a kind of collaborative learning (e.g., communicative approach, task-based learning).

Additionally, according to Lightbown and Spada, students are more likely to improve their performance and grow their language proficiency in a collaborative setting than they would be able to do on their own¹. By Moon, who describes pair work as a method "to organize them (students) in ways that will maximize learning opportunities," another definition that connects pair work to learning is provided. Working in pairs thereby enhances and encourages meaningful engagement amongst the students, increasing their language output. As a result, encouraging pair work as a productive method improves students' language output when it comes to speaking assignments. Storch divided the categorization of pair work groups into four distinct dyadic interaction types. They were expert/novice, dominant/passive, collaborative, and dominant/dominant. The best sort of relationship interaction is collaborative².

¹ Doff, A. Teach English: A Training Course for Teachers, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998.

² Long, M. & Porter, P. Group work, inter language talk and second language acquisition". TESOL Quarterly, 19.2 (1985): 207-228.

At this point, kids are collaborating well and are ready to share ideas. Storch also noticed that collaborative pair work involved more language selection discussions, more feedback exchanges, and more confirmation checks. Another favorable grouping within pair workgroups was expert-novice. The knowledge was passed from an expert to a novice. One was the teacher, and the other was taking classes. This kind of pair work engagement benefited students in both types of roles. The dominant/dominant pattern was not well-liked. Learning was not taking place in this scenario. It's possible that neither student is listening to the other and that they are not exchanging ideas. Another drawback was the dominant/passive relationship, in which one student was not learning because the partner was not engaging them actively. Students who work in pairs can benefit much from one another. There are always strong and weak students in a class. When pairing up the students, the teacher should keep in mind that there may be a mix of students with varying skill levels in one group. With this in mind, he or she can forecast which responsibilities would be best for specific students as well as what they may educate their peers about before assigning the assignments.

Additionally, they teach their peers a ton of brand-new words and phrases. The main advantage of pair work is that it gives students more practice time. As a result, kids begin engaging in alternative activities in place of honing their English, such as talking, doing their homework, or even playing cards. If the teacher does not recognize and stop it in time, this results in general chaos. The teacher should assign an activity to the entire class. Twenty people communicate at once during pair work, as opposed to just one during teacher-led activities. Because of this, students utilize the language and its new words more frequently the more pair work activities they participate in. The amount of language practice students receive during group projects varies on the activity type. The learner's confidence is a further vital benefit of pair work. There are several reasons to think that pupils might feel more at ease speaking a foreign language to one or two persons as opposed to the entire class and the teacher³.

Particularly shy pupils or those who are still developing their language skills feel more at ease and self-assured when they try to put their language skills to the test during the activity and observe how they use them. Students are encouraged to work together as a result of this. They believe they are to blame for the achievement. This is frequently observed during group tournaments as the students collaborate for the good of the entire team. There is no way for timid or weak students to dodge or avoid cooperating; they must work together and support one another. The fact that everyone is participating in

³ Underwood, J. & Underwood, G. Task effect on cooperative and collaborative learning with computers. In K. Littleton & P. Light (Eds.), *Learning with Computers: Analyzing Productive Interaction* (pp. 10-23). London: Routledge.

the activity is yet another crucial aspect of pair work. Pair work helps pupils' fluency grow as well. As was already mentioned, in a regular classroom, kids do not have a lot of opportunities to practice the language. Following the presentation of new grammatical constructs, the teacher assigns activities or drills that are related to the newly learned material. If the practice is meaningless, the students perform it mechanically and without thinking, and they can quickly forget it within a week or a month. They do not improve their speaking abilities, much less their fluency in a foreign language. Instead, pair work has an impact on these skills.

The language is open for use by the pupils, who are allowed to express their ideas and opinions. It's challenging to avoid having the notion that fluency can only be achieved by consistent speaking practice in an environment of independence and ease. The benefits of pair work extend to teachers as well as students. They initially save time. He or she can divide the class into pairs and have them complete the exercise at the same time rather than assigning each student to practice a structure or respond to the questions individually. Students are able to use the language more during the course as a result. The teacher may teach more content and engage pupils in more activities when time is saved. The kids will undoubtedly love this because they won't have time to become bored thanks to the range of activities and their own involvement in the class. The lecture will appear more engaging as a consequence, the teacher will be well-liked by the kids, and the teacher will take pleasure in his or her employment because it will complete him or her⁴.

Pairwork could be a useful tool for monitoring pupils' learning progress. The teacher can accomplish this without the kids being aware that they are being watched and tested. The teacher can assess the student's ability to communicate in a foreign language by moving around the room and listening to each speaker. In addition to noting the most frequent errors for discussion later, this allows the teacher to assess the class as a whole. This information aids the teacher in determining whether lessons need to be repeated or further clarified. Pair work allows the teacher to examine the lesson plan and prepare materials for the next phase of the class, which is another significant benefit. Although the teacher may be well-prepared for the session, occasionally he or she may just forget what needs to be done next.

The finest lesson plan research activities are in pairs. It is also useful for setting up the resources for the upcoming activity, such as putting images or passages from the literature on the wall or writing something on the chalkboard. Pair work, according to

⁴ Maher, K. Intricacies of pair work – surveys and research. Bulletin of Keiwa College, 20 (2011): 15-32.

some educators, has a lot of drawbacks for both teachers and students. One issue is that students frequently converse in their home tongue. If there are forty people in the class, it is tough to get rid of this.

Conclusion. These classroom setups appear to have as many drawbacks as benefits, and since every instructor has different preferences, it is impossible to say with certainty which one is best. He or she can decide for themselves which one to employ when teaching a language. Nobody should be coerced into using pair work. Therefore, saying that pair work is the best method for honing language abilities is quite inconvenient.

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